

Appendix 4 Task Force DEI Environmental Scan Findings

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Table 1. Policies, Positions, and Activities by Organization

Organization	Policies/Positions	Activities
AcademyHealth (AH) http://www.academyhealth.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blog post: Diversity and Inclusion in Health Services and Policy Research: Then, Now, and the Future (7/29/20) • No institutional policies published on the Website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funded the Center for Diversity, Inclusion, and Minority Engagement (AMIA member Margo Edmunds, director) in 2013 • Sponsored 2014 roundtable that led to the 2015 report “The Future of Diversity and Inclusion in Health Services and Policy Research: A Report On The AcademyHealth Workforce Diversity 2025 Roundtable” • Launched HSR Workplace Culture Study (bad link?) • AcademyHealth Diversity Scholars Network (travel, registration support for AH meetings)
American Academy of Family Physicians (AAFP) www.aafp.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity in the Workforce • Medical Schools, Underrepresentation in Medicine • Equal Representation of Women in Family Medicine • Equal Opportunity • Membership Evaluation, Discrimination in • Fairness in Federal Programs For All U.S. Citizens • Sensitivity to Diversity and Cultural Proficiency in AAFP Education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The EveryONE Project, a multi-part project that includes support for a diverse workforce • Committed to enhancing content and editorial processes to reflect DEI in <i>American Family Physician</i> • “FM Residency Diversity Can be Fast-Tracked” and “Matching Our Mission: A Strategic Plan to Create a Diverse Family Medicine Residency” in 2019 • “Board Certified Family Physician Workforce: Progress in Racial and Ethnic Diversity” in 2018
American Academy of Emergency Medicine (AAEM) www.aaem.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A policy of ensuring diversity on AAEM’s Ethics Committee • Members-only content could not be accessed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A standing Diversity, Equity, Inclusion Committee that publishes journal articles on DEI topics • A podcast on physician burnout, racism, and corporate misrepresentation • A podcast on how AAEM advocates for women and minorities • Released a statement with the Society for Academic Emergency Medicine on the death of George Floyd
American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) www.aap.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Published “Enhancing Pediatric Workforce Diversity and Providing Culturally Effective Pediatric Care: Implications for Practice, Education, and Policy Making” in 2013 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established the AAP Staff Diversity and Inclusion Council to “serve as a sounding board for ideas and act as an ambassador for diversity and inclusion initiatives and opportunities to benefit the AAP workforce”

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members-only content not accessed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Produced "lunch and learn" programs with internal and external speakers to explore DEI topics Published in 2013 a survey of backgrounds of 2010 graduating pediatric residents Published in 2015 a survey about diversity training efforts and perceptions in pediatrics departments
American Academy of Physician Assistants (AAPA) www.aapa.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiated a Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion CME Webinar Series Convenes a Commission on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (2020-21 charges)
American Association of Nurse Practitioners (AANP) www.aanp.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity Commitment Statement Members-only content, including policies, not accessed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiated a Diversity and Inclusion Committee (info behind firewall) Implemented RUN 2 Nursing to help minority students from rural and/or disadvantaged backgrounds to succeed
American Association of Physician Specialists (AAPS) www.aapsus.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None found
American College of Surgeons (ACS) www.facs.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Statement on Diversity Diversity at ACS Statement on Harassment, Bullying, and Discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Committee on Diversity Issues Equity, Diversity and Inclusion Workgroup Created a set of diversity resources to promote workplace diversity Impact of Diversity on Physician Resiliency webinar (members-only)
American Health Information Management Association (AHIMA) www.ahima.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resolution on Diversity AHIMA and Diversity Management (members-only) Diversity and Inclusion Statement (bottom of page) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None found
American Hospital Association (AHA) www.aha.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Published dozens of articles about the importance of diversity Is "affiliated" with the Institute for Diversity and Health Equity Offers Certificate in Diversity Management (?)
American Medical Association (AMA) www.ama-assn.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategies for Enhancing Diversity in the Physician Workforce D-200.985 Ensuring Diversity in USMLE Exams D-275.963 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advisory Committee on LGBTQ Issues Minority Affairs Section Women Physicians Section

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eliminating Questions Regarding Marital Status, Dependents, Plans for Marriage or Children, Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity, Age, Race, National Origin and Religion During the Residency and Fellowship Application Process H-310.919 • Continued Support for Diversity in Medical Education D-295.963 • Diversity of AMA Delegations G-600.030 • Underrepresented Student Access to US Medical Schools H-350.960 • The Demographics of the House of Delegates G-600.035 • Diversity in the Physician Workforce and Access to Care D-200.982 	
American Medical Women's Association (AMWA) www.amwa-doc.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section of Diversity and Inclusion (similar to committee) • Gender Equity Task Force
American Nurses Association (ANA) www.nursingworld.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing a Culturally Competent Master's and Doctorally Prepared Nursing Workforce • Racial Justice for Communities of Color • Nursing Advocacy for LGBTQ+ Populations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minority Fellowship Program • Diversity in Nursing award • Diversity Awareness resources (?) • Affiliations with related organizations (e.g., Orthodox Jewish Nurses Association) • Continuing education
American Osteopathic Association (AOA) http://osteopathic.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AOA Statement Denouncing Racism and Inequality + revision w/additional co-signers • Promoting Diversity in AOA Membership and Leadership • AOA Statement Regarding Offensive FIGS Ad • America's Frontline Physicians Urge Trump Administration to Protect Transgender Patients and Women's Reproductive Health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint Statement on Addressing Racism Through Collective Action in Obstetrics and Gynecology • Published 10 Recommendations for a Diverse and Inclusive Osteopathic Medical School 	
American Pharmacists Association (APA) www.pharmacist.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found
American Physical Therapy Association (APTA) www.apta.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nondiscrimination policy • APTA President’s statement on Racism and Systemic Inequality in America • APTA Commitment to Diversity, Equity and Inclusion • Position Paper: The Allied Health Work Diversity Act 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Celebration of Diversity Virtual Gala to support the Minority Scholarship Fund • Diversity, Equity and Inclusion standing committee • Campaign for Future Generations • Dimensions of Diversity Fund • Hiring of a Director of Inclusion (2021) • Lynda D. Woodruff Lecture on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in Physical Therapy
American Telemedicine Association (ATA) www.americantelemed.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found
Association of American Indian Physicians (AAIP) www.aaip.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found
Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) www.aamc.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing and Eliminating Racism at the AAMC and Beyond • AAMC Statement on Executive Order on Combatting Race and Sex Stereotyping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity and Inclusion Strategic Planning Toolkit • Minority Student Medical Career Fair • Racism and Health: A Reading List • Workshop: Understanding Allyship and Responding to Microaggressions Through Bystander Intervention • Mid-Career Minority Faculty Leadership Seminar • Group on Women in Medicine and Science Leadership Award • Group on Diversity and Inclusion Exemplary Leadership Award • Group on Diversity and Inclusion • Diversity in Medicine: Facts and Figures 2019 publication • Promising Practices for Understanding and Addressing Salary Equity at US Medical Schools

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility, Inclusion, and Action in Medical Education: Lived Experiences of Learners and Physicians With Disabilities
Association of Black Women Physicians (ABWP) www.blackwomenphysicians.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breonna Taylor Statement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentoring Program • Charity & Scholarship Benefit
Association of Medical Professionals with Hearing Losses (AMPHL) www.amphl.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision Statement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentoring Program • Statistical Registry • Stethoscope Comparison Tools
College of Healthcare Information Management Executives (CHIME) https://chimecentral.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity and Inclusion Committee
GLMA (GLMA) www.glma.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same-Sex Marriage and Health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare Equality Index project • Marriage Equality Initiative • Compendium of Health Profession Association LGBTQ Policy & Position Statements • Physician Survey Project • LGBT Health Achievement Awards
Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society (HIMSS) www.himss.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Health Equity Network African American Community • Global Health Equity Network Latinx Community • Women in Health IT Community
National Council of Asian Pacific Islander Physicians (NCAPIP) www.ncapip.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NCAPIP Stands with the African American Community and Denounces Police Brutality and Murder • COVID-19 Treatments Must Work for Communities of Color • NCAPIP Joins Community Leaders Condemning Discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLAS in the Workforce – Cultural and Linguistically Appropriate Services in Health Care presentation • Research Leadership Training Program
National Hispanic Medical Association (NHMA) www.nhmamd.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COVID-19 Treatments Must Work for Communities of Color • Statement of the Trump Administration Rollback Health Care Protections for Vulnerable Communities During COVID-19 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentoring Program • College Health Scholars Program • National Hispanic Leadership Agenda
National Medical Association (NMA) www.nmanet.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NMA Statement on the Breonna Taylor Grand Jury Decision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Council on Concerns of Women Physicians

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statement from the NMA on the Passing of C.T. Vivian and Congressman John Lewis • Statement Urging HHS to Collect, Analyze, Release COVID-19 Data on Mortality by Race, Ethnicity 	
National Osteopathic Medical Association (NOMA) https://nomaonline.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found
Society of Hospital Medicine (SHM) www.hospitalmedicine.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found
Society of Healthcare Professionals with Disabilities (SHPD) https://www.disabilitysociety.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None found 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functions as a clearinghouse of resources created by others

Table 2. Policies and Positions by Type

Type	Policy/Position	Organization(s)
Diversity	Diversity in Health Services Research (blog)	AH
	Diversity in the Workplace/Workforce	AAFP, AAP, AMA (2), APTA
	Sensitivity to Diversity and Cultural Proficiency in Association Education	AAFP
	Diversity on Institutional Ethics Committee	AAEM
	Statement on/Commitment to Diversity/DEI	AANP, ACS, AHIMA (2), APTA
	Diversity in Medical Education, Certification Exams	AMA (2), AOA
	Diversity in Association Delegations, Delegates, Leadership	AMA (2), AOA
	Establishing a Culturally Competent Masters and Doctorally Prepared Nursing Workforce	ANA
Discrimination	Discrimination in Membership Evaluation	AAFP
	Fairness in Federal Programs for All Citizens	AAFP
	Statement on Harassment, Bullying, and Discrimination	ACS
	Eliminating Discriminatory Questions in the Residency, Fellowship Application Process	AMA
	NCAPIP Joins Community Leaders Condemning Discrimination	NCAPIP
	Nondiscrimination	APTA
Equal Opportunity	Equal Opportunity	AAFP
Representation	Underrepresentation in Medicine, Med Schools	AAFP, AMA
	Equal Representation of Women in Medicine	AAFP
Racism	Racial Justice for Communities of Color	ANA
	Statement Denouncing Racism and Inequality	AOA, APTA
	Statement on Addressing Racism Through Collective Action in Ob/Gyn	AOA
	Addressing and Eliminating Racism at the AAMC and Beyond	AAMC
	AAMC Statement on Executive Order on Combating Race and Sex Stereotyping	AAMC
LGBTQIA+	Nursing Advocacy for LGBTQ+ Populations	ANA
	Statement on the Protection of Transgender Patients and Women's Reproductive Health	AOA
	Same-Sex Marriage and Health	GLMA
Sexism	AAMC Statement on Executive Order on Combating Race and Sex Stereotyping	AAMC
Other Policies and Statements	Statement Regarding Offensive Advertising	AOA
	Statement on the Death of George Floyd	AAEM

Breonna Taylor Statement	ABWP
NCAPIP Stands with the African American Community and Denounces Police Brutality and Murder	NCAPIP
COVID-19 Treatments Must Work for Communities of Color	NCAPIP, NHMA
Statement of the Trump Administration Rollback Health Care Protections for Vulnerable Communities During COVID-19	NHMA
NMA Statement on the Breonna Taylor Grand Jury Decision	NMA
Statement from the NMA on the Passing of C.T. Vivian and Congressman John Lewis	NMA
Statement Urging HHS to Collect, Analyze, Release COVID-19 Data on Mortality by Race, Ethnicity	NMA, AMA, AAP, AAFP, NHMA, AAIP, NCAPIP

Table 3. Activities by Type

Type	Activity	Organization(s)
Committee/Task Force	DEI committee/commission	AAEM, AAP, AAPA, AANP, ACS (2), AMWA, APTA, AAMC, CHIME
	Advisory committee on LGBTQ issues	AMA
	Gender equity task force	AMWA
	Marriage Equality Initiative	GLMA
DEI Center	Funding of a center for DEI	AH
Meeting/Roundtable/ Panel	Sponsorship of DEI roundtable	AH
	Lunch and learn programs about DEI	AAP
	Workshop on understanding allyship and responding to microaggressions through bystander intervention	AAMC
Research/Surveys	Workplace culture/training study	AH, AAP
	Survey of graduating residents' backgrounds	AAP
	Diversity in Medicine: Facts and Figures 2019	AAMC
	<i>Promising Practices for Understanding and Addressing Salary Equity at US Medical Schools</i>	AAMC
	Statistical Registry	AMPHL
	Stethoscope Comparison Tools	AMPHL
	AMA/GLMA Physician Survey Project	AMA, GLMA
	Compendium of Health Profession Association LGBTQ Policy & Position Statements	GLMA
	Accessibility, Inclusion, and Action in Medical Education: Lived Experiences of Learners and Physicians With Disabilities	AAMC
	Professional Education	Strategic plan for DEI in medical residency
Program to help minority students from rural backgrounds to succeed	AANP	
DEI CME/CE	AAPA, ANA	
Certificate in Diversity Management	AHA	
Minority fellowship program	ANA	
Named lecture in diversity	APTA	
Minority student medical career fair	AAMC	
Mid-career minority faculty leadership seminar	AAMC	
Mentoring program	ABWP, AMPHL, NHMA	
Research Leadership Training Program	NCAPIP	
Professional Groups	Diversity scholars network	AH
	Minority affairs section	AMA
	Women members section	AMA, HIMSS, NMA

	Affiliation with other DEI group	AHA, ANA
	Global Health Equity Network African American Community	HIMSS
	Global Health Equity Network Latinx Community	HIMSS
	National Hispanic Leadership Agenda	NHLA
Diverse Workforce Promotion	Project supporting a diverse workforce	AAFP
	Workforce assessment	AAFP
	Hiring of Director of Inclusion	APTA
	Diversity and inclusion strategic planning toolkit	AAMC
	CLAS in the Workforce – Cultural and Linguistically Appropriate Services in Health Care	NCAPIP
Fundraising	Celebration of Diversity Virtual Gala	APTA
	Campaign for Future Generations	APTA
	Dimensions of Diversity Fund	APTA
	Charity & Scholarship Benefit	ABWP
	College Health Scholars Program	NHMA
Awards	Diversity award	ANA
	Group on Women in Medicine and Science Leadership Award	AAMC
	Group on Diversity and Inclusion (GDI) Exemplary Leadership Award	AAMC
	LGBT Health Achievement Awards	GLMA
Benchmarking Awareness Raising	Healthcare Equality Index	GLMA
	Efforts to reflect DEI in association publication	AAFP
	Podcast/Webcast on DEI topics	AAEM, ACS
	Diversity resource development	ACS, ANA
	Racism and Health: A Reading List	AAMC